

Piṅgalāmata chapter 8, edition

A f66r, line 7; B57r, line 3; C f32v, line 10.
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bhairava uvāca

- 8.1 vāstusūtraṃ pravakṣyāmi yathā kṣetre vyavasthitam
sūtraṃ kārpaśikaṃ caiva kṣaumaṃ bālbajavalkajam
- 8.2 śubhārthe tu śubhā hy ete samasūtrās trivartanāt
gulmagranthivihīnaṃ ca avyāviddham avīkaram
- 8.3 aśubhe kośajaṃ śāṅasnāyucarmajam eva vā
snāyuvellyān tathā cauraṃ paṭṭasūtram athāpi vā
- 8.4 gulmagranthisamāyogād yathākarmānusārataḥ
vilomavartanaṃ caiva dvirāvartaṃ tathaiva ca
- 8.5 tad ādau marmavijñānaheto vāstuṃ prasārayet
matakṣetrasamaṃ kṛtvā jalapūrṇaṃ niśāmukhe
- 8.6 citrasvātyantare tārā kiṃ cid uccā tu sā bhavet
kṛtvā dīpaṃ tadagre śāṅkuṃ kṛtvā tadagrataḥ

A f66v

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

2b sama] BC; sasa A

• tri] AB; ti C

2d avīkaram] conj.; acīkaram ABC

3a śāṅa] AB; śāla C

5a vijñāna] AB; vijñānaṃ C

5b hetor] C; heto AB

5c kṣetra] BC; kṣetraṃ A

5d pūrṇaṃ] A; pūrṇa BC

6b uccā] AB; utthā C

6d śāṅkuṃ] conj.; chaktaṃ C; cha[[śa]]ktaṃ] B; chaṃktaṃ A

- 8.7 śaṅkucchāyāvibhāgena pūrvāparaṃ vilakṣayet
brahmasthānaṃ vilakṣyādau sādhyasūtraṃ nipātayet
- 8.8 dakṣiṇottaram anyac ca mīnayugmaṃ dhruveṇa vā
mataḥsetrārdhadiksūtraṃ samsthe syād vidiśāṃ grahaḥ C f33r
- 8.9 tatra mīnacatuṣkaṃ tu sidhyate 'tra na samśayaḥ
mīnān mīnasthasūtreṇa sidhyate caturaśrakam
- 8.10 navanāḍivibhaktam tu kṛtvā sūtraṃ prapātayet
śriyā yaśovati kāntā supriyā vimalā śivā
- 8.11 suśobhā bhā nunī caitā nāḍyaḥ prācīmukhodgatāḥ
dhanyā dhanā viśālā ca sthirā bhadrā gadā niśā B f57v
- 8.12 virajā vibhavā caiva uttarasthānam āgatāḥ
nāḍyaṣṭādaśasamyogāc catuṣṣaṣṭipadaṃ bhavet

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

with 10c-12b, compare Anantaśambhu, commentary to the Siddhāntasārāvalī, 150
(taken from SŚ part 3 587):

prāgagrāṇy uttarāgrāṇi vāstoḥ sūtrāṇi nāḍyaḥ
lakṣmīr yaśovati kāntā svapriyā vimalā śivā
subhagā sumatī sārā nāḍyaḥ prācīmukhodgatāḥ
dhanyā prāṇā viśālā ca sthirā bhadrā jayā niśā
virajā vibhavā caitā nāḍyaḥ saumyamukhāḥ smṛtāḥ

7d sādhyā] AB; madhye C

8b dhruveṇa] BC; dhruvena A

8c sūtraṃ] BC; sūtra A

8d grahaḥ] AB; gra{haḥ} C

11a caitā] em.; cetā ABC

11b mukhodgatāḥ] AB; mukho{dgatāḥ} C

11d niśā] BC; niśāḥ A

12b āgatāḥ] BC; āgatā A

- 8.13 pārsvavaṃśo 'rdhavaṃśaś ca durjayo durdharo dvayam
agnir vāyugataś caiva durjayaḥ parikīrtitaḥ
- 8.14 īśarakṣagato bhadre durdharas tu na saṃśayaḥ
rajjavo 'ṣṭau smṛtāś cānyās tāś cākhyābhir yathā śṛṇu
- 8.15 karṇau gulphau ca dvau sandhī tripadās te prakīrtitāḥ
kīlanī bandhanī caiva karṇagau gulphagau priye
- 8.16 srjanī caiva pakṣī ca dakṣagau vāmagau tathā
pañcakoṣṭhagatāś cānyā hṛdamśau kaṭimanugau
- 8.17 pārsvage vāpi dve prokte rajjutadrajjuvogataḥ
saṃvartī ca vivartī ca hṛdyavaṃśakaṭijānugā
- 8.18ab dakṣapārsvagatā pakṣī sadbhāvā vāmagā matā

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

with 15, compare Anantaśambhu, commentary to the Siddhāntasārāvalī, 150
(taken from SŚ part 3 587):

karṇayoḥ pādagulphe ca krīḍanī bandhanī tataḥ
saṃvartā ca vivartā ca jānukurparasamgame
hṛdguhyakukṣimārgeṣu sadbhāvā janānīti ca
pakṣī yakṣīti vijñeyā rajjavo 'ṣṭau ca nāmataḥ

13a vaṃśo 'rdhavaṃśaś] em.; vaṃśārdhavaṃśaś CC; vaṃśorddhaśaś A

14a rakṣa] BC; rakṣo A

14c rajjavo 'ṣṭau] A; raktacoṣṭau B; raktacāṣṭau C

• cānyās] A; cānyā BC 14d śṛṇu] BC; śṛṇuḥ A

16b vāmagau] AC; vāvāmagau B

16d kaṭimanugau] B; kaṭimanugauḥ A; kaṭimamtragau C

17a pārsva] AC; prārśva B • prokte] em.; prokta A; prekto B; yuktā C

- 8.18cd padmaṃ vajras tu sandhiś ca padaṃ lāṅgalasaṃpuṭam A f67r
- 8.19 triśūlaṃ maṇibandhaś ca trikaṭaṃ svastikaṃ tathā
vaṃśaṃ rajjumayaṃ nāḍyaṃ marmatrayodaśakaṃ smṛtam
- 8.20 sūtrāṣṭayuk smṛtaṃ padmaṃ pañcasaṃkhyāṃ prakīrtitam
brahmasthānāditaḥ kṛtvā pūrvayāmyāparottare
- 8.21 ṣaḍbhiḥ sūtragato vajra aṣṭāviṃśa sa ucyate
nāḍisaṃpātako yo 'tra sandhimarmas tu sa smṛtaḥ
- 8.22 saṃkhyā ṣoḍaśa ity uktā sandhīnāṃ tu varānane
śuddhakoṣṭhaṃ padaṃ proktaṃ caturviṃśati tat smṛtam
- 8.23 rajjusūtraṃ savāṃśaṃ ca tasyārdhe halaṃ smṛtam
tasya saṃkhyā varārohe ṣoḍaśaivam udāhṛtā

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

18c padmaṃ] em. Harunaga Isaacson; padmaṃ ca ABC

19a śūlaṃ] A; śūla BC

19c vaṃśaṃ] BC; vaṃśa A

• nāḍyaṃ] BC; nā[[ma]]ḍya A

20a padmaṃ] A; padma BC

21a vajra] BC; vajraḥ A

21d marmas tu] AB; marmasu C

• sa smṛtaḥ] A; saṃsmṛtaḥ BC

22a uktā] BC; aktā A

22c koṣṭhaṃ] BC; koṣṭha A

23b halaṃ] B; phalaṃ AC

23d udāhṛtā] BC; udāhṛtāḥ A

- 8.24 koṇāt koṇagataṃ sūtraṃ saṃpuṭaṃ tan na saṃśayaḥ
dvātriṃśaṃ tu tad evoktaṃ nātra kāryā vicāraṇā
- 8.25 koṇe trisūtraṃ yac ca śūlaṃ tan nātra saṃśayaḥ
turyasaṃkhyāṃ tad evoktaṃ īśāgnītīraṃ priye
- 8.26 sūtrapañcakasaṃyogān maṇibandhaḥ sa ucyaṭe
vasusaṃkhyāḥ sa evoktaḥ pūrvādaḥ yugmayugmakāḥ
- 8.27 tasyānugaṃ trisūtraṃ ca trikaṭaṃ tan na saṃśayaḥ
pañca saṃkhyā yathāpūrvāṃ taddiśāyāṃ udāhṛtaṃ
- 8.28 rajjuyuk padamadhye tu svastikaṃ tan na saṃśayaḥ
atra vāstau na tad uktam uktaṃ syād yatra saṃbhavet
- 8.29 vaṃśadvayaṃ purāproktaṃ rajjavo 'ṣṭau tathaiiva ca
nādyasṭādaśakaṃ marma kathitaṃ tatra suvrate

B f58r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 24c triṃśaṃ] AC; triśaṃ B
 24d vicāraṇā] C; vicāraṇāt AB
 25c saṃkhyāṃ] A; saṃkhyā B; saṃkhyā C
 26a sūtra] AB; maṃtra C
 26c saṃkhyāḥ] BC; saṃkhyāḥ A
 28cd uktam uktaṃ] BC; uktamuktaṃ A
 19a dvayaṃ] A; dvaya BC
 29b ca] BC; caḥ A

- 8.30 marmopabhedas tv anyac ca marmadvayasamāgamāt
devatāsthānakam karma rākṣasānām tathaiva ca
- 8.31 devatārākṣasāsandhi na pīḍyam marmakam kvacit
padme sampīḍite caiva sarvanāśas tu jāyate
- 8.32 vajre sampīḍite svāmivināśam caiva jāyate
sandhau sampīḍite caiva vyādhipīḍā tu jāyate
- 8.33 pade sthānavināśaḥ syād vāhanāya ca sambhavet
lāṅgale pīḍite caiva dhānyakṣayam samādiśet
- 8.34 sampuṭe pīḍite kartur duḥkhatrayasamādiśet
triśūle pīḍite caiva patnībhrāṭṛsutakṣayaḥ
- 8.35 maṇibandhe tu pañcatvam yānti bhṛtpāḥ prapīḍite
trikaṭe mitraviprāṇam gavām pīḍā nṛpasya ca
- 8.36ab svastike ca tathā viddhe tad rāṣṭre ca parābhavam A f67v

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

30a tv anyac ca] BC; tvaccanya A

31a sandhi] AB; samdhir C

33a syād] C; syāt AB

35d ca] BC; caḥ A

36b rāṣṭre] B; rāṣṭe AC

8.36cd vaṃśe saṃpīḍite caiva kṣayī vaṃśas tu paitṛkaḥ

8.37 rājjuṇīde tathā vaṃśe mātrke kṣayam ucyate
nāḍīviddhe tu sarvāṅgo viśīryati ca nityaśaḥ

8.38 marmopadharmasambhinne sarvaṃ phalam ihāvahet
na pīḍayet tathā devān rākṣasāṃś caiva suvrate

C f33v

8.39 tatkāle pūjayed devān baliṃ caiva pradāpayet
pūjitāḥ pātītā hy ete sukhaduḥkharāḥ smṛtāḥ

8.40 rājño rāṣṭrasya kartuś ca sthāpakasya ca nityaśaḥ
mahābhayakaro vedhas tasmād etān na pīḍayet

8.41ab evaṃ jñātvā sprśen marma kuḍyastambhādibhir na ca

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

36d paitṛkaḥ] BC; paitṛkaṃ A

37a pīḍe] AB; pītā C

37c sarvāṅgo] C; sarvāṅgaḥ B; sarvāṃga A

38b ihāvahet] AB; ihābhavet C

39c pātītā] BC; pātītāḥ A

40a kartuś] BC; karttuṃś A

40c vedhas] AC; vedhaḥ B

40d etān] A; etan BC

piṅgalovāca

8.41cd ko vā vāstusamākhyāto dehas tasyaiva kīdṛśaḥ

8.42 kiṃnimittaṃ tu te devās tac charīre samāśritāḥ
śarīrāvayavās tasya prākṛtā vaikṛtās tathā

8.43 ke te devāḥ kathaṃ tatra saṃkhyā saṃjñā pṛthak pṛthak
kṣetre caiva tathā rūpaṃ tathā kathaya śaṅkara

B f58v

bhairava uvāca

8.44 viṣṇor varāharūpeṇa pṛthivī coddhṛtā yadā
tadotpannādrayaḥ sarve mahākāyā mahābalāḥ

8.45 śaśirāḥ pakṣasaṃyuktā durjayā durdharāḥ priye
khagāsino nagāḥ sarve prajāvibhramakārah

8.46 utpannā niyatantaś ca nipatya pṛthivītale
prajān nipātayanty ete pakṣānilasamāhatāḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

before 41c piṅgalovāca] BC; piṅgalaüvāca A

42b samāśritāḥ] C; samāśṛtāḥ B; samāśṛtāḥ A

43a devāḥ] AC; devā B

43c tathā] BC; yathā A

43d śaṅkara] em.; śaṅkaraḥ] ABC

44a viṣṇor] AC; viṣṇo B

44b pṛthivī] A; pṛthvī BC

44c tadotpannādrayaḥ] BC; tadotpannādrayaḥ A

45a saṃyuktā] AC; saṃyuktāḥ B

46c prajān] em.; prajā ABC

• nipātayanty ete] AB; nipātayatvena C

- 8.47 munisiddhāpsarodaityā naranāgādayas tathā
tatas tu ṛṣayas trastā hanyamānā mahānagaiḥ
- 8.48 vyāso vālmikaśākalyaḥ parāśarabhr̥gus tathā
nāradas tumburuś caiva śālaṅkāyanakauśikaḥ
- 8.49 vālahilyādayaḥ sarve gatā yatrendraḥ saṁsthitaḥ
gatvā divaṁ surendrasya purato barhatāḥ prabho
- 8.50 teṣāṁ hi vacanaṁ śrutvā saṁkruddhaḥ pavipāṇikaḥ
kariṇaḥ skandam ārūḍhaḥ śaktim udyamya bhāsurām
- 8.51 rūpeṇājaghnivān bhīmo harir nagavarūthinīm
prāpnāś caiva mahāghoraṁ saṁgrāmaṁ surasattamaiḥ
- 8.52 nagaiḥ saha durādharṣair gīrvāṇākulakāribhiḥ
utpatya praharanty āśu pakṣaghātānilāhatāḥ
- 8.53 devās tad īdṛṣe yuddhe hariṇā vajrapāṇinā A f68r
vyomni pakṣaśiracchedaśaktinā tvaritena tu
- 8.54 patitā bhūmim ākramya nirghāte va hi sundari
teṣāṁ dharābharākrāntā śeṣādyāś ca nipīditāḥ

Ω = AB(→C)

- 47a daityā] AC; daityāḥ B 47c tatas] BC; tataḥs A
• trastā] BC; tatra A 48a vālmika] AB; vālmika{ḥ} C
48b parāśara] AB; parāśaro C 48c tumburuś] AC; tumburaś B
48d śālaṅkāyana] A; sālaṅkāyana B; sālaṅkāyanaḥ C
49a vālahilyādayaḥ] BC; vālaśikhyādayaḥ A 49b gatā] C; gatāḥ AB
• yatrendraḥ] em.; yatrenda ABC
49d barhatāḥ] AB; ba[–]tāḥ C 50b pavipāṇikaḥ] AB; paripālakaḥ C
52a durādharṣair] A; durādharṣaiḥ BC 52c āśu] C; āśuḥ AB
53a tad īdṛṣe] AB; tutādṛṣe C 53c śiaccheda] AB; śiraścheda C
53d śaktinā] conj.; śaktināṁ] AB; śaktināṁ C 54a patitā] AB; pati{tā} C

- 8.55 muñcanti garalaṃ sāsṛk koṣṇaṃ caiva sabāṣpajam
tadviṣāghrātam ākrāntā dharā mūrchām upāgatā
- 8.56 kṣaṇaikam mūrchām āsthāya sasarjoṣṇaṃ mahānilam
viṣāś cānilasaṃyogād yatotpanna tu suvrate
- 8.57 viṣolvaṇamahādvaraḥ kāyo nāma mahāsuraḥ
adhruvāntaṃ śarīraṃ tu prākṛtaṃ caiva suvrate
- 8.58 tenārkendugrahā dakṣāś candrāgnimañijātayāḥ
diśāvāyur dharākāśapānīyaṃ gaganāṅganam
- 8.59 chādītā nābhībhaṣante divi devāś ca pakṣiṇaḥ
pṛthivyāṃ munayaś caiva yogasiddhāpsarogaṇaḥ
- 8.60 na sandhyā na divā rātrau na velā na tu tarpaṇam
dhyānapūjājapo nāsti na diśābalikarma ca

B f59r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

55b koṣṇaṃ] AB; koṣṭhaṃ C

55d upāgatā] BC; upāgatāḥ A

56b sasarjoṣṇaṃ] AB; sasarjoṣṭaṃ C

58a tenārkenđu] A; tenār kodu B; tenār kodur C

• grahā dakṣāś] C; grahādakṣāś B; grahātmakṣāś A

58c diśā] BC; diśāṃ A

58d gaganāṅganam] C; gag[[ā]]anāṃgaṇaṃ B; gaganāṃganāṃganāṃgaṇaṃ A

59c munayaś] AC; munaya[[ḥ]]ś B

60c dhyāna] BC; dhyānaṃ A

- 8.61 tad ākulamanāḥ sarve gatā yatrāmbikāpatiḥ
gatvā stotraṃ samārabdham ṛgyajuḥsāmātharvaṇaiḥ
- 8.62 huṃphaṭkāravaṣaṭkārair gadyapadyair anekaśaḥ
stutvā bhavaṃ bhavānīm praṇatāḥ śaraṇaṃ gatāḥ
- 8.63 stotraṃ brahmāditaḥ śrutvā cāvīrbhūto bhayāndhakṛt
pratyakṣaṃ bhagavan drṣṭvā surā jānum upāgatāḥ
- 8.64 trāhi indra dhareśāna bhagnās te vibudhādhipāḥ
uktaṃ kajodbhavenaitat surendraviṣṇunā tathā
- 8.65 sarvaārtiharo nāthaḥ sarvaduḥkhāpahāraḥ
kim etad bhūtaṃ nātha naṣṭacandre varṣavārī
- 8.66 brahmādivacanaṃ śrutvā teṣāṃ budhvāśayaṃ mahat
devyā coktaṃ tu he nātha niyāmedaṃ mahāsuram

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

61a manāḥ] C; manā B; manās A

61b gatā] BC; gatāḥ A

61c stotraṃ] AC; stotu B

61d yajuḥ] C; yaju A; yarju B

63a stotraṃ] AB; stotra C

63b cāvīrbhūto] BC; cāvībhūto A

64a indra] BC; indraṃ C

64b te] C; tā AB

65d varṣavārī] em.; varsavārī B; varśavarī C; vasarvarī A

66b budhvāśayaṃ] AC; budhvāsvayaṃ B

66c tu he] conj.; [-]he C; he AB

- 8.67 devyāś ca vacanaṃ śrutvā budhvā caivākulān surān
bho mahendrāḥ prakurvadhvaṃ dṛḍhavaśāś ca rajjavaḥ
- 8.68 sthīrasattvā balaṃ vadhvaṃ yenedaṃ saṃyamāmy aham
svāminaś ca vacaṃ śrutvā hr̥ṣṭāḥ sarve manotsukāḥ
- 8.69 tato dhyānena saṃcintya bhairaveṇa mahātmanā
rudraṃ cātibalaṃ nāma mahāmāyaṃ sa sṛṣṭavān
- 8.70 anujñāṃ prārthayitvā tu mahāmāyo gato bhṛśam
tenākṛṣyordhvavṛttiṃ mahādaityasya suvrate
- 8.71 keśair ākṛṣya jānubhyāṃ bhairavāgre nipātitaḥ
tatottāne saśiras tu karau saṃkocya jānukau
- 8.72 datvā vaṃśaṃ tathā rajjuṃ viṣkambhasadṛśikṛtaḥ
vaikṛtaṃ tu śarīredaṃ kṣetre vā kṣetravad bhavet

C f34r

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

68a devyāś] A; devyā BC

67c mahendrāḥ] em.; mahendrā BC; marendrāḥ A

67d vaśāś] BC; vaśāc A

68c vacaṃ] C; vaca AB

68d hr̥ṣṭāḥ] C; hr̥ṣṭā AB

• manotsukāḥ] em.; mano{tsu}kāḥ C; manocchukāḥ AB

69b mahātmanā] B; mahātma{nā} C; mahātmanāḥ A

69c cātibalaṃ] AB; cātibalaṃ C

69d sa] AB; saḥ C

70b gato] A; gatā BC

71c tatottāne] AB; tatojnāne C

• saśiras C] ; śaśiras A; sasiras B

71d jānukau] B; jānukauḥ A; jānugau C

- 8.73 bhayojjitamanāḥ sarve devās tatropatiṣṭhitāḥ A f68v
 īśakoṇe sa parjanya vahnipūṣau tu vahnigau
- 8.74 piṭṛdauvārikau caiva ītikōṇe vyavasthitau B f59v
 vāyunāgau tathā vāyoḥ padārdhārdhe vyavasthitāḥ
- 8.75 jayo mahendrakaś caiva ādityaḥ satyakas tathā
 bhṛśāntarīkṣaṃ padikāḥ pūrve caiva vyavasthitāḥ
- 8.76 vitatho dakṣiṇe caiva gṛhakṣatayamas tathā
 gāndharvo bhṛṅgahariṇaḥ padaikavibhavās tv ime
- 8.77 sugrīvaḥ śragvijaś caiva pracetasāsuras tathā
 śoṣarogas tathā paṅktipadikāḥ paścime sthitāḥ
- 8.78 mukho bhalvāṭakaḥ somo rigiś caivāditir ditiḥ
 uttare padikāpaṅktiḥ saṃsthitās te yathā śṛṇu

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

73a manāḥ] AC; manā B

73c koṇe] BC; kauṇai A

74a dauvārikau] AB; hotārikau C

74c vāyoḥ] BC; vāyauḥ A

75a mahendrakaś] BC; māhemdrakaś A

74b iti] AB; iti C

75c bhṛśāntarīkṣaṃ] conj.; bhṛśāntarīkṣā ABC

76b gṛhakṣatayamas] conj.; gṛhakṣatamayas A; [– –]gṛhayamas C; gṛhayamas B
 • tathā] BC; tathāḥ A

76d tv ime] AC; tvikeme B

78c paṅktiḥ] AC; paktiḥ B

- 8.79 catuṣkoṣṭhātmabhūr madhye tadīṣe cāpasamsthitih
tasyeṣe cāpavatsas tu dvipadau tau prakīrtitau
- 8.80 brahmāgnige ca sāvitri dvipadāntāṃ vilekhayet
tadagnige ca savitā so 'pi syād dvipadasthitah
- 8.81 kajodbhavetidigbhāge dvipadendras tu samsthitah
tasyāpīigate caiva indrajid dvipade sthitah
- 8.82 ‡ ‡ rājayaḥsmā ca dvipade ca vyavasthitah
tasyāpīigate caiva rudradāsapadadvikah
- 8.83 brahmāpūrve caturyāṃśair marīcako vyavasthitah
teṣāṃ yāmye vivasvā ca somāpye cottare dharah
- 8.84 carakīṣe bāhyataḥ koṇe vidāry agnidiśas tathā
pūtanetidiśābhāge vāyavyāṃ pāparākṣasī

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

79a koṣṭhātmabhur] AB; koṣṭhātmanur C

79b samsthitih] em.; samsthitah ABC

80b vilekhayet] BC; vilepayet A

81a kajodbhave] AB; kaḍobhave C

81c tasyāpīti] BC; tasyāpīta B

82a ketāṇe A; kerāṇe B; kerale C

• rāja] A; gaja BC

82c tasyāpīigate] A; tasyāpīragate B; tasyāpīajate C

83c yāmye] A; yāmyeva B; yā[-]va C

• vivasvā] AB; vivaṃvā C

83d somāpye AB; somāya C

84a carakīṣe] AB; caraṇīṣe C

- 8.85 pūrvādīg bāhyataḥ skando aryamā dakṣiṇe tathā
jambhāpye ca tathā bhūya uttare pilapiṃcchakaḥ
- 8.86 sthitā saṃdhāraṇārthāya nānyathāpiṣṭhayāṃ sthitiḥ
prajojanaṃ sthitiḥ kāryā karaṇīyo vāstur ucyaṭe
- 8.87 paryāyaiḥ pañcabhir nāma vastutvaṃ vāstusaṃkhjñakam
avastu prākṛtaṃ proktaṃ anarthākaraṇā sthitiḥ
- 8.88 akāryaṃ ceti paryāye vastvādi vaikṛtocyate
sthitam vāstudharāṃ vyāpya kṣetraṃ vyāpya yathepsitam
- 8.89 prāsāde caiva prakāre purāṭṭālakatoraṇe
stambhe brahmaśilāyāṃ ca gṛhe dvārapraveśataḥ
- 8.90 maṭhe rājagṛhe vātha purāvāsakasamyute
nagare grāme kheṭake vā viṣaye deśasamcaye
- 8.91ab yatra yatreṣṭasadbhāvas tatra vāstuaṃ prakalpayet

B f60r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

85a bāhyataḥ] BC; bāhyata A

85c jambhāpye ca] A; jambhāpyeva BC

85d pilapiṃcchakaḥ] BC; pilapiṃcchakā A

86b nānyathāpiṣṭhayāṃ] AB; nānyathāpiṣṭhayāṃ C

86c kāryā] C; kāryāḥ AB

88c sthitam] em.; sthito ABC

89c śilāyāṃ] BC; śilāyāś A

89d praveśataḥ] A; [-]praśataḥ C; praśataḥ B

90c grāme] BC; grāma A

• kheṭake] BC; kheṭe A

91a bhāvas] AC; bhāvaḥ B

91b vāstuaṃ] AC; vāstu B

8.91cd catuḥṣaṣṭipadaḥ proktaḥ prāsāde caturaśrakaḥ

8.92 same rūpavinirmuktā śukāghrā valabhīs tathā
stambhe brahmaśilāyāṃ ca vṛṣabhasya catuṣkike

A f69r

8.93 evamādi same caiva vedāśre vedavad bhavet
mervādu cchandakānāṃ tu rūpaṃ padyasya kīrtitam

8.94 graharakṣaprayoktavyaṃ jñātvā sthānavibhāgaśaḥ
abhyantare yathā pūrvaṃ vedāśraṃ parikalpayet

8.95 meror meruvad vāstur mandareva hi mandaraḥ
kailāsavāstunāmā ca kailāseva hi kīrtitaḥ

8.96 sarvatobhadravaj jñeyaḥ sarvatobhadrasaṃjñayā
vimāno nāma yaḥ prokto vimāneva hi kīrtitaḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

92a same] A; samai BC

• muktā] em.; mukto BC; mukt[[e]ā A

92b valabhīs tathā] BC; valabhi[[tha]]stathā A

94c pūrvaṃ] AC; pūrva B

95a meror] AC; me[[ru]]ror B

• vāstur] A; vāstu BC

95b mandaraḥ] em.; mandiraḥ ABC

95d kīrtitaḥ] BC; kīrtitāḥ A

96a bhadravaj] C; bhadravat AB

96c prokto] C; proktaḥ AB

- 8.97 nandivardhanavan nandivardhaneva hi nandanah
siṃhākāreva siṃhas tu gaje caiva gajākṛtiḥ
- 8.98 padmākāreva padmas tu aṣṭāśraṣoḍaśas tathā
vardhamānas tu yo vāstu vardhamāneva kīrtitaḥ
- 8.99 śrīvatsēva hi śrīvatsavāstuś caiva tridhā bhavet
bhadra vad bhadrasaṃjñas tu haṃsavad dhaṃsa eva ca
- 8.100 nalino nāma yo vāstur nalineva hi kīrtitaḥ
bhadra vad gṛharājas tu śrīnageva hi śrīnagaḥ
- 8.101 eteṣāṃ cchandakānāṃ tu graharaḥṣaṃ prakalpayet
śeṣānye pūrvaṃ nyāso diśāsu vidiśāsu ca
- 8.102 jñātvā bhāgaṃ prakartavyaṃ prabhūte prabhūtaṃ tathā
tatsame tatsamo yojyo nyūne nyūnaṃ prakalpayet

C f34v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

98c vāstur] em.; vāstu ABC

99a śrīvatsēva] BC; śrīvaccheva A

• śrīvatsa] BC; śrīvaccha A

99d ca] BC; tuḥ A

100a vāstur] AC; vāstu B

101b rakṣaṃ] em.; rakṣa ABC

101c pūrvaṃ] AB; pūrva C

• nyāso] AB; nyāsā C

- 8.103 kumbho vṛṣo 'tha gvāvṛkṣas teṣāṃ caivādhunā śṛṇu
svamataṃ kṣetramānaṃ tu kumbhavat parivartayet
- 8.104 madhye tu dhruvakam kṛtvā trinemi bhrāmayet samam
prāgāpyaṃ brahmasūtraṃ ca pātayed dakṣiṇottaram
- 8.105 bāhye nemīpadaṃ caiva aṣṭāviṃśati kārayet
dvitīyaṃ padaṃ viṃśaṃ tu tṛtīye dvādaśaṃ tathā
- 8.106 caturthe turyasaṃkhyātaṃ catuḥṣaṣṭipadaṃ bhavet
jaleśau vahnipūṣau tu pitṛdauvārikau tathā
- 8.107 vāyunāgaṃ yathāpūrve nyased īśāditaḥ kramāt
śeṣānāṃ pūrvavan nyāso brahmādyānte yathā purā

A f69v

B f60v

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 103c mataṃ] BC; mata A
 103d kumbhavat] BC; kuṃbhaṃbhavat A
 104b nemi] AB; nemair C
 104d dakṣiṇottaram] AC; dakṣiṇottaraṃḥ B
 105c dvitīyaṃ] A; dvitīye BC
 • padaṃ] em.; pada ABC
 • viṃśaṃ] A; viśaṃ BC
 106a saṃkhyātaṃ] BC; saṃkhyāta A
 106c vahni] BC; vahi A
 106d dauvārikau] em.; dvauvārikau ABC
 107b īśāditaḥ] AC; īśādita B
 107d purā] AC; purāḥ B

- 8.108 īśetyadhordhvago vaṃśaḥ pārśve cāgnīragas tathā
īśād yamāpyage caiva ityāḥ prāguttare tathā
- 8.109 agner uttarage cāpye iragā dakṣapūrvage
rajjavo 'ṣṭau smṛtā hy etāḥ pūrvādīn pūrvavad yathā
- 8.110 grahādīn pūrvavad bāhye diśāsu vidīśāsu ca
vṛttavāstuḥ smṛto hy eṣa vṛttākārāśrayaḥ priye
- 8.111 aindraliṅgasya vajrasya prāsādaś caturaśrakaḥ
vāstuś caiva tathāproktaḥ pūrvavat samudāhṛtaḥ
- 8.112a āgneyasya ca liṅgasya

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 108a īśetyadhordhvago] AB; īśetyādhārdhago C
108b pārśve] C; pārśveś B; pārśvaś A
108c yamāpyage] A; yamāpyago B; yamāpsaraś C
108d ityāḥ] em.; ityā AB; ityā C
• uttare] AC; ure B
109a cāpye] B; cāpya A; cāsyā C
109b iragā AB; iragā C
109c etāḥ] C; etā B; eto A;
109d pūrvādīn] C; pūrvādīt AB
110c vāstuḥ] C; vāstu AB
110d vṛttākārāśrayaḥ] AC; vṛttākārā[[h]]śrayaḥ B
111a aindra] BC; aindri A
111b prāsādaś] em.; prāsādaś A; prāsāda BC
111c vāstuś] AC; vāstu B
• proktaḥ] AC; prokta B
112a āgneyasya ca] AC; āgneyasya B

8.119cd rakṣorājasya liṅgasya khaḍgākhyasya ca suvrate

8.120 prāsādas tryaśrakaś caiva vāstuś caiva tathā bhavet
svamataṃ kṣetramānaṃ tu pūrvavat tryaśrakaṃ kuru

8.121 guṇavat tryaśrakaṃ madhye samamānavikalpitaḥ
pūrvavat koṣṭhakān kalpya pūrvavad devatā nyaset

8.122 vaṃśarajjus tathā proktā marmādiḥ pūrvavad yathā
guṇakoṇāśrayāṇāṃ tu trikoṇo vāstur bhāṣitaḥ

B f61r

8.123 koṇaikaṃ paridhistaṃ tu kuṇḍavat taṃ vikalpayet
vāruṇasya ca liṅgasya pāsāliṅgasya suvrate

A f70r

8.124ab prāsādaḥ kumbhavat khyāto vāstuś caiva puroditaḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

119d khaḍgākhyasya] A; khaḍmakhyasya B; ṣaḍmukhyasya C

121c koṣṭhakān] AB; koṣṭakāṃ C

121d devatā] em.; devatāṃ ABC

122a proktā] em.; prokto BC; proktoḥ A

122d koṇo] A; koṇa C; ko B

124a prāsādaḥ] em.; prāsādaṃ BC; prāsādaṃ A

- 8.124cd vāyuliṅgadhvajasyaiva ṣaṭkoṇaś cāśrayo hitaḥ
- 8.125 ṣaṭkoṇaṃ pūrvavat kṛtvā kṣetraṃ caiva tu sundari
tribhir ante tathā kuryāt samamānavilakṣitam
- 8.126 samaḥ ṣaṣṭhamakoṇaś tu paridhistho varānane
aṣṭāvīṃśas tathā viṃśadvādaśaś catur eva ca
- 8.127 catuḥṣaṣṭipado 'trāpi pūrvavad devatā nyaset
vaṃśarajjus tathā bhadre marmādīn pūrvavad yathā
- 8.128 grahādīn bāhyatas tadvad diśāsu vidīśāsu ca
ṣaḍaśrakāśrayāṇaṃ tu ṣaḍaśro vāstuḥ kīrtitaḥ
- 8.129 kauberasya ca liṅgasya gadāliṅgasya suvrate
padmaprāsādas tv ākhyāto vāstuś caiva tathā bhavet
- 8.130 padmaprāsādavat kṣetraṃ kṛtvā caiva yathā purā
dvau dvau padmāśrī rajjvādīn bāhye caiva prakalpayet
- 8.131 vṛttavan madhyato vāstur yathāpūrvam udāhṛtaḥ
padmākṛtyāśrayāṇaṃ tu vāstuḥ padmākṛtir bhavet

C f35r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

Between 131b and 131c, B reads: [[vṛttavanmadhyatovāpistuyathāpūrva]]

125a koṇaṃ] AC; koṇa B

125d vilakṣitam] A; vilakṣitaḥ BC

126a ṣaṣṭhama] AB; ṣaṣṭama C

• koṇaś] BC; koṇaś A

126c viṃśas] BC; viṃśa[[ti]]s A

126d dvādaśaś] AB; dvāda{śa}ś C

127a ṣaṣṭi] C; ṣaṣṭhi AB

• 'trāpi] AB; tridhāpi C

127b devatā] em.; devatāṃ ABC

127c marmādīn] BC; marmādīn A

128a tadvad] AC; tadvat B 129c ākhyāto] A; {ā}khyāto C; akhyāto B

131a vṛttavan] AC; vṛttavat B • vāstur] em.; vāstu ABC

131b udāhṛtaḥ] A; udāhṛtam C; udāhṛta B 131d vāstuḥ] em.; vāstu ABC

- 8.132 aiśānyasya ca liṅgasya śūlaliṅgasya suvrate
aṣṭāśraś cāśrayaḥ vāstuś caiva tathā bhavet
- 8.133 aṣṭāśraṃ pūrvavat kṛtvā paridhithāṣṭamam bhavet
kṣetraṃ turyāśrakam bāhyo vistaras tu dvidham bhavet
- 8.134 tribhiś cānte tathā kuryād aṣṭāśraṃ parikalpanā
pūrvavat koṣṭhakān bhājya nyāsaś caiva tathā bhavet
- 8.135 vaṃśaṃ rajjuṃ tathā kuryān marmādīṃś caiva lakṣayet
aṣṭāśraś cāśrayāṇaṃ tu aṣṭāśro vāstuḥ kīrtitaḥ
- 8.136 brahmātmake bhavet pīṭham suśiraṃ syāt tadantataḥ
dvibhāgāc ca bhaved bhittir bhāgādīś caiva tadvidhaḥ
- 8.137 vaiṣṇavasya tu liṅgasya cakrāṅkasya suvrate
garuḍo nāma prāsādo vāstuś caiva tathā bhavet

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

132a aiśānyasya] BC; aiśānya[[ca]]sya A

133a aṣṭāśraṃ] B; aṣṭāśraṃ C; aṣṭāśra A

133c bāhyo] A; bāhye BC

133d vistaras tu dvidham] conj.; vistaratudvidham A; vistarāṃtadvidham BC

135a vaṃśaṃ] A; vaṃśa BC

• kuryān] BC; kuryāt A

135b marmādīṃś] BC; marmādīś A

135c cāśrayāṇaṃ] em.; cāśrayāṇaṃ C; cāśrayāṇān B; cāśrayāyāṃ A

135d vāstuḥ] C; vāstu AB

136b syāt] AC; syā B

- 8.138 brahmaliṅgasya padmasya haṃsākhyas tv āśrayo mataḥ
vāstuś caiva tathā bhadre prāsādākṛtilakṣaṇaḥ
- 8.139 prāsādaliṅgavedīnām yeṣāṃ bhāgo yathā gataḥ
teṣāṃ tathā grhīto 'pi kāryāḥ śobhā yathā bhavet
- 8.140 athavā samamānena jaṅghāntaṃ caiva kārayet
yasya yat kīrtitaṃ rūpaṃ tadrūpeṇa varaṇḍakam
- 8.141 maṇḍapās tu tathā proktā ye te proktās tu sādhanē
caturaśrādibhedena prāsādākṛtilakṣaṇāḥ
- 8.142 taddiśābhāgavikṣiptās tatkāryakaraṇe hitāḥ
tadvaktrabhāvamantrās ca tadvat sthāpya prasādhayet

B f61v

A f70v

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

139a prāsāda] em; prāsāda A; prasāda BC

• liṅga] AB; liṅgaṃ C

139d kāryāḥ] conj. kāryā ABC • śobhā] A; śo[_] C; śo B

140d varaṇḍakam] AC; varaṇḍakaṃḥ B

141a maṇḍapās] A; maṇḍapā BC

• proktā] BC; proktāṃ A

141b ye te] AB; ete C

141d prāsādākṛtilakṣaṇāḥ] BC; prāsākṛtilakṣaṇām A

142c bhāva] AB; bhāga C

142d sthāpya] AC; sthā[[na]]pya B

- 8.143 kṣetrānyad rudravād bhaktaṃ nāḍibhis tu nibodha ma
aindrī pūrve samākhyātā yāmyā dakṣiṇataḥ sthitā
- 8.144 paścime tu jayā proktā saumye saumyāṃ vidur budhāḥ
prāñnāḍibhir vibhakte tu bāhyasthāś catasro 'tra tu
- 8.145 vaṃśadvayaṃ tathātrāpi turyarajjus tathaiva ca
tripadāś caiva boddhavyās turyānyā padasaptagāḥ
- 8.146 tathā marmādikaṃ jñeyaṃ devatānyāsa ucyate
carakī ceśakoṣṭhe tu skandaś caiva tathānugaḥ
- 8.147 agnikoṣṭhe vidārī ca aryamā ca tathā bhavet
nairṛtyāṃ pūtanāṃ nyasya jambhaṃ caiva tadānugam
- 8.148 pāparākṣasīm vāyavyāṃ pilipicchaṃ tathaiva ca
dvitīye īśakoṣṭhe tatreśaṃ vinyased budhaḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

143d sthitā] em.; sthitāḥ ABC

144b saumyāṃ] A; saumyā BC

• vidur] AC; vidu B

144c prāñ] C; prāg AB

144d catasro 'tra] AC; cataśrotra B

146c ceśa] A; veśa BC

147c pūtanāṃ] A; pūtanā BC

147d jambhaṃ] AC; jāmbha B

• tadānugam] AC; tadānugaṃḥ B

148a vāyavyāṃ] AC; vāyavyā B

148b pilipicchaṃ] em.; pilipiccha B; pilipicchas C; pilapicchan A

- 8.149 agniṃ caiva tathā nyasya pitaraṃ vāyum eva ca
parjanyaḍi bahiḥpaṅktir dityantaṃ caiva suvrate
- 8.150 devāṣ caiva caturviṃśad dvipadāṣ te prakīrtitaḥ
devāṣtau padikā jñeyāḥ ṣeṣānte tu yathā purā
- 8.151 nagarākhyāḥ smṛto vāstur nagarārambhe tu suvrate
asya pūrve yadā liṅgaṃ bhogamokṣaprasiddhidam
- 8.152 paścimāsyāṃ tathā kuryāt tathaiśāgnī vidur budhāḥ
nagarāpye yadā liṅgaṃ tadā pūrvamukhaṃ bhavet
- 8.153 vāyvīṭige tathā proktaṃ prāṇmukhaṃ parikalpayet
dakṣasaumye tu vīpsātaḥ pūrvāparamukhau 'pi vā
- 8.154ab madhye caiva tadā proktaṃ vīpsākāravikalpanā

B f62r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

149c parjanyaḍi] A; paryanyaḍi BC

150a catur] AB; tathā C

150d purā] AC; purāḥ B

151a vāstur] C; vāstu AB

152c nagarāpye] A; [[pūrvamukha]]nagarāpye B; nagarāsyē C

153a īṭige] em.; īṭage BC; ībhage A

153d mukhau] BC; mukho A

154a proktaṃ] AC; prokta B

- 8.154cd sāmānyasādhane nyāsaḥ prāsādaṃ kathayāmi te
- 8.155 prāsādaṃ vṛṣabho nāma pūrve caiva vikalpayet
āgneyyāṃ kumbhako nāma yāmyadig valabhī bhavet
- 8.156 nairṛtyāṃ khagarājas tu gvāvṛkṣam āpye kalpayet
ṣoḍaśāśras tu vāyavyāṃ gajo nāma ca saumyagaḥ
- 8.157 aiśānye sarvabhadras tu bhogamokṣaprasādhakāḥ
śeṣānye ca yathābhiṣṭaṃ sthāpyo meruḥ purāntataḥ
- 8.158 anyad deśātmakaṃ vāstuṃ yathāvat tat tathā śṛṇu
catustrimśaḥ smṛtā nāḍyaḥ samantāc caturaśrakaḥ
- 8.159 trayastrimśatpado jñeyas tatra jāyati suvrate
prāñnāḍyanugatā nāḍyaḥ saṃjñābhir vividhaiḥ sthitāḥ

C f35v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

154d prāsādaṃ] BC; prāsādāṃ A

155d valabhī] AB; valabhīr C

156b vṛkṣam āpye] BC; vṛkṣasāpya A

156d gajo] AB; gaje C

• nāma] em.; nāmā ABC

• saumyagaḥ] em.; saumyago C; saumyage AB

158a anyad] AB; anya C

158c nāḍyaḥ] AC; nāḍyadyaḥ B

159c prāñ] C; prāg AB

- 8.160 padam atra sahasraṃ daśaikonaśatānvitam
sapādadvitaye pañktau grahādīn bāhyato nyaset
- 8.161 pañcatriṃśatpadaiḥ koṇe pādādhikayā tu rākṣasī
pādūnā ca caturtriṃśad grahānām prāgdiśāditaḥ
- 8.162 pādūnāntāś catuṣ pañktir īśādyā devatāḥ priye
īśāgnīti tathā vāyur īśakoṇādiśam nyaset
- 8.163 caturdaśapadair bhāgaḥ pādādhikyam prakalpayet
padaikādaśikānyeṣām pādādhikyam jalādīnām
- 8.164 bhinnasūtrasmṛto hy eṣa devānām rākṣasaiḥ saha
āpavatsādikānām te padāṣṭādaśikām nyaset
- 8.165 marīcyādyādharāntāś ca catuṣpañcāśikātmakāḥ
ekāśītipadānte tu brahmā tatra pratiṣṭhitaḥ

A f71r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 160a atra] AB; aṃtra C 160b daśaikona] C; daśaikonna AB
161b pādādhikayā] A; pādādhīpātkā B; pādādhīpā[-] C
• rākṣaṣī] A; rakṣasī BC 161c catus] BC; catu A
162a catuṣ] C; catuḥ AB 162b devatāḥ] C; devatā AB
162d koṇā] C; koṇo A; kośā B
163d jalādīnām BC; jalādīnāḥ A
164b rākṣasaiḥ saha] C; rākṣasaiḥsaha[[ḥ]] B; rākṣasaiḥsahaḥ A
164c āpavatsādikānām te] AC; āpavatsādikāntanānte B
165b catuṣ] C; catuḥ AB
• pañcāśikātmakāḥ] BC; pañcāśikātmikāḥ A

- 8.166 vaṃśadvayaṃ yathābhūtaṃ rajjuṃ caiva śṛṅṣv atha
navātmikā smṛtā turyā turyānyāś caturvimśagāḥ
- 8.167 marmādīni yathāpūrvam tathā samyag vilakṣayet
deśārambhe smṛto hy eṣa padair yojanakalpanā
- 8.168 maṇḍalātmā bhaved yas tu tadārambhe tu suvrate
kr̥te daśasahasrāṅke vāstau caiva sureśvari
- 8.169 yaduktaṃ caiva paṅktyākhyaiḥ koṣṭhakair daśadhātmakaiḥ
carakīśe śataṃ caiva skandaś caiva tathānugaḥ
- 8.170 vidāryagneḥ śataṃ dadyād aryamā ca tathānugaḥ
pūtanetiśataṃ dadyāj jambhaś caiva tathānugaḥ
- 8.171 pāparākṣasivāvyāyāṃ pāde caiva śate bhavet
tasyāpy anugataṃ tadvat pilipicchaṃ vidur budhāḥ

B f62v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

166c turyā] conj.turya ABC

169a yad] BC; yaḥ A

• paṅktyākhyaiḥ] AC; paktyākhyaiḥ B

169b daśadhātmakaiḥ] BC; daśadhātmikaiḥ A

169c śataṃ] em.; sataṃ ABC

169d skandaś] BC; skandaṃ A

171b pāde] AC; pād[[ai]ē B

171d pilipicchaṃ] em.; pilapicchaṃ] AB; pailapicchaṃ C

- 8.172 carakyante śate caiva īśānaṃ ca vidhānataḥ
vidāryante tathā vahneḥ koṣṭhakaiḥ śatakalpanā
- 8.173 pitarah pūtanānte tu pade caiva śate bhavet
vāyoḥ śatapadaṃ dadyāt tathānte pāparākṣasī
- 8.174 parjanya dviśataṃ dadyāj jaye caiva tathā bhavet
māhendre dviśataṃ bhadre tathāditye vidur budhāḥ
- 8.175 satyāya dviśataṃ dadyād bhṛśāya dviśataṃ bhavet
śataṃ caivāntarīkṣāya vahner bāhye prakalpayet
- 8.176 pūṣāya dviśataṃ dadyād vitathāya tathaiva ca
dviśataṃ grhakṣetrāya yamāya dviśataṃ bhavet
- 8.177 gandharvāya tathā bhadre bhṛṅgāya dviśataṃ punaḥ
ītibāhye śateśāya dauvāriko hy ataḥ param
- 8.178 dviśataṃ ca yathā kalpya sugrīvo dviśato bhavet
puṣpadantas tathā bhadre pracetasi tathaiva ca

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

174a parjanya] AC; pa[[rya]]rjanya B

174d tathāditye] BC; tathāditya A

174d vahner] BC; vahne A

176d yamāya] BC; ya A

177c śateśāya] AC; śataśāya B

177d dauvāriko] C; dvāuvāriko B; dvauvāriko[[h]] A

178b dviśato] BC; dviśate A

- 8.179 asuraḥ śoṣasaṃjñāś ca dviśataṃ dviśataṃ bhavet
vāyavānte tu śataṃ dadyād rogāyātra na saṃśayaḥ
- 8.180 nāgāya dviśataṃ bhadre mukhyāya dviśataṃ punaḥ
bhalvāṭasya tathā kalpya somāya dviśataṃ bhavet
- 8.181 dviśataṃ rigidevāya aditaye tathaiva ca
īśānte tu śataṃ dadyād ditaye 'tra na saṃśayaḥ
- 8.182 āpavatsādiko bhadre rājyānto dviśate bhavet
marīcyādīdharāntaṃ tu vedasaṃkhyāśatānvitā
- 8.183 catuḥśatenātmabhūr madhye samyak caikaṃ prakalpayet
vaṃśadvayaṃ tathābhūtaṃ rajjavaḥ śatarāmagāḥ
- 8.184 turyasaṃkhyā tathānyāpi śatamunigatā bhavet
marmādīṃś ca tathātrāpi jñātvā maṇḍalakaḥ

A f71v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

179a śoṣasaṃjñāś ca] em.; śoṣasaṃjñāyo C; śoṣasaṃjñāyaḥ B; sosusaṃjñāca C

180b mukhyāya] BC; mukhyā A

181c dadyād] BC; dadyāt A

182a āpavatsādiko] C; āpavacchādiko AB

182b rājyānto] em.; rāyāṃto A; rājānto BC

183a bhūr] A; bhū BC

184b śata] BC; śataṃ A

184c marmādīṃś] AC; marmād[[i]]īṃś B

• tathātrāpi] A; tathāpi BC

184d kalpanā] BC; kalpanāḥ A

- 8.185 pattanārthe tu yo vāstuḥ pattanākhyam prakalpayet
aṣṭāśītyardhasamṣuktam śatam caiva vidur budhāḥ
- 8.186 sūtratrīdaśasampātāt koṣṭhair dvādaśakair bhavet
bhūtasamkhyāpadādhiṣṭhā carakī ceśakoṇataḥ
- 8.187 aindre tu ṣaṭpadaiḥ skando vidārī bhūtam agnige
ṛtvāvastho 'ryamā yāmye pūtanetiśārānvitā
- 8.188 jambhāpye rasāvasthas tiryage pāparākṣasī
pṛthivyādika saumye tu pilipiccho rasānviṭaḥ
- 8.189 punarantaḥsamīpeśaḥ padaṃ ekaṃ bhunakti saḥ
parjanya jayamahendrau dvipadās te prakīrtitāḥ
- 8.190 turyāvastho raviprokto dvipade satyako bhṛśaḥ
antarikṣaḥ padāvastho vahnir āgnau tathaiva ca

B f63r

C f36r

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

185a vāstuḥ] em.; vāstu A; vastu BC

185b pattanākhyam] A; pattanākhyā BC

185c samṣuktam] A; yuktaṃtu BC

186d koṇataḥ] AB; kośataḥ C

187a skando] em.; skanda ABC

187c 'ryamā] BC; ryamāṃ A

188a jambhāpye] AB; jambhāsye C

188c pṛthivyādika] AB; pṛthivyadika C

189b bhunakti saḥ] em.; bhunaktiśaḥ A; tunaktiśaḥ BC

189c mahendrau] em.; māhendra ABC

190c antarikṣaḥ] em.; antarikṣa A; antarīkṣa BC

190d āgnau] AB; agnau C

- 8.191 pūṣā vitathanāmā ca dvipado 'tha gṛhaksataḥ
vedādhiṣṭho yamaś caiva gandharvo bhṛṅgiḥ pakṣavat
- 8.192 hariṇā padam ekaṃ tu pitaro 'pi tathaiva ca
dauvāriko 'tha sugrīvaḥ sragdharo dvipadās tv ime
- 8.193 yamavad varuṇāvastho daityaśoṣaś ca yugmavat
rogaikaṃ ca tathā vāyur nāgo mukhyas tv ataḥ param
- 8.194 bhalvāṭo dvipadās te tu somas turyapadānviṭaḥ
rigyādityau tathā bhūyo dvipadau tau prakīrtitau
- 8.195 ditiḥ pade tu bodhavyaṃ śeṣānte tu yathā purā
vaṃśadvayaṃ tathābhūtaṃ rajjuś cāṣṭau śṛṇuṣv atha
- 8.196 tripadās turyasaṃkhyātās turyānyā tāragā matā
marmādīṃś ca yathāpūrvam jñātvā pattanam ārabhet

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

191d gandharvo] em.; gāndharvo ABC

• bhṛṅgiḥ] em.; bhṛṅgi ABC

192c dauvāriko] em.; dvaouvāriko ABC

192d sragdharo dvipadās] em.; sragdvijodvipadās C; śragdvijodvipadās B;

śragdvipadās A

193a yamavad varuṇāvastho] AB; yamavatkaruṇāvastho C

193c rogaikaṃ] A; rāgaikaṃ BC

• vāyur] C; vāyu AB

193d mukhyas] BC; mukhyaḥs A

194a bhalvāṭo] em.; bhalvāṭā ABC

194b somas turya] AB; somasūrya C

194c bhūyo] em.; bhūya ABC

194d prakīrtitau] AC; pr[[ā]]akīrttitau B

195a ditiḥ] A; diti BC

195b tu yathā purā] AC; turyathāpurāḥ B

196a tri] AC; stri B • saṃkhyātās] A; saṃkhyātā{ḥ} C; saṃkhyātā B

196b matā] BC; matāḥ A

196c marmādīṃś] AC; marmādīś B

• pūrvam] C; pūrvv[[āḥ]]am A; pūrva B

- 8.197 anyañ khetātmako nāma vāstuś caiva sureśvari
nāḍīdvādaśasampātāt koṣṭhaikādaśakair bhavet
- 8.198 sarvaṃ saṃpiṅḍite caiva viṃśaikayuk śataṃ bhavet
bahiḥ paṅkteś caturdikṣu carakyādigrhaiḥ saha
- 8.199 bhūtasamkhyāpadāvastho diśāsu vidiśāsu ca
dvitīyapaṅktibhoktāram īśādyam kathayāmi te
- 8.200 īser īsaṃ suvinyansya parjanyas tadanantaram
jayo māhendrakam nyasya ravisatyam tathaiva ca
- 8.201 bhṛśāntarīkṣam vinyasya pāvake 'gniṃ vidur budhāḥ
pūṣā vitathanāmā ca grhakṣatayamas tathā
- 8.202 gandharvo bhṛṅgahariṇo yakṣodik pitaram nyaset
dauvāriko 'tha sugrīvaḥ sragdharo 'tha pracetasah

A f72r

B f63v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

197a anyañ] em.; anyam ABC

197d koṣṭhaikādaśakair] AB; koṣṭhakādaśakair C

198a sarvaṃ] BC; sarvva A 198b yuk śataṃ] BC; yucchataṃ A

198c paṅkteś] AC; pakteś B

198d carakyādi] BC; ca[[tu]]rakyādi] A

• grahaiḥ] BC; grahais A

• saha] C; sahaḥ AB

199c dvitīyapaṅkti] A; dvitī{ya}paṅkti C; dvitīyapakti B

200a īser] AB; īśair C

201a bhṛśāntarīkṣam] A; bhṛśāntarīkṣam BC

201d yamas] BC; mayas A

202a bhṛṅga] BC; bhṛṅgi A

202b pitaram] AC; pitara B

202c dauvāriko] em.; dvauvāriko AB; dvaudvāriko C

202d sragdharo] conj.; sargdviyo C; śragdviyo AB

- 8.203 asuraśoṣarogāś ca vāyau vāyur vijānataḥ
nāgamukhyaṃ tathā nyasya bhalvāṣasomam eva ca
- 8.204 ṛgyaditiditiṃ nyasya vatsādīn pūrvavan nyaset
yadpadānte marīcyādy ā brahmā navapadāntataḥ
- 8.205 vaṃśadvayaṃ yathāpūrvam tripadās turyarajjavaḥ
turyānyāṣṭapadā jñeyā marmādīn pūrvavad yathā
- 8.206 samyag jñātvā varārohe kheṭārambhaṃ samācāret
grāmavāstum pravakṣyāmi grāmārambhe tu suvrate
- 8.207 bhadrātmakaṃ kṛtaṃ kṣetraṃ pūrvāpyekaṃ vināśayet
padaikūnaśataṃ bhadre tatra jāyanti nānyathā

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

203a asura] A; asuraḥ BC

203b vāyur] C; vāyuṃ A; vāyu B

204a aditiditiṃ] A; adityaditiṃ BC

205c turyānyāṣṭa] AB; turyānyāṣṭa C

206a samyag] C; samyak AB

206b kheṭārambhaṃ] AC; kheṭārambha B

206d grāmārambhe] BC; grāmāraṃbhaṃ A

207c padaikūna] AB; padaikena C

207d tatra] AC; tatraṃ B

- 8.208 carakī pilipicchas tu jambho vai pāparākṣasī
saumyapañktigatās te tu grahāḥ sārhadvibhāgikāḥ
- 8.209 yāmyapañktau tathābhūtau vidāryādīn prakalpayet
īśādīn pūrvavan nyasya vatsādīṃś ca tathaiva ca
- 8.210 marīcyādīṃś tathā nyasya brahmā madhye tathaiva ca
vaṃśadvayaṃ nipātyādau tripadās turyarajjvaḥ
- 8.211 turyānyāṣṭapadā jñeyā kiṃ tu madhye vivarjanāt
marmādīṃś ca tathā budhvā grāmārambhaṃ samārabhet
- 8.212 athānyaṃ saṃpravakṣyāmi koṭṭāṭṭālakasaṃyutam
kṛte śatapade kṣetre pūrvasthaṃ dvipadāntataḥ
- 8.213 tatpakṣe tripadaṃ lopya tiryag dairghyaṃ padaṃ tu tat
īśagne tu pade sthāpya tadadhaḥ pakṣavat tyajet

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

208a pilipicchas] BC; pilipicchiṃś A

208b jambho] BC; jambhau A

• pāparākṣasī] BC; pāparākṣī A

208c saumya] BC; saumyaṃ A

• pañkti] AC; pakti B

209a pañktau] AC; paktau B

209d vatsādīṃś] C; vatsādīś AB

210a marīcyādīṃś] C; marīcyādīś AB

210c dvayaṃ] em.; dvaya ABC

211a turyānyāṣṭapadā] em.; turyānyāṣṭapadā ABC (compare with: 205c
turyānyāṣṭa] AB; turyānyāṣṭa C)

213c sthāpya] AB; sthāpye C

213d pakṣavat tyajet] em.; pakṣavatyajet ABC

- 8.214 dairghyaṃ tiryak padaikaṃ tu savyāsavyaṃ vidur budhāḥ
īśāgnau yatpadau bhadre bhāgārdhārdhāvibhājītau
- 8.215 carakīskandamūrdhnisthau vidāryaryamapāvake
pūtanetidiśābhāge padaṃ pūrṇaṃ bhunakti sā
- 8.216 tasyottarapade jambhaḥ pāparākṣasi tiryage
tasyāpīndragate picchampīlāśabdādi paśya vai
- 8.217 carakyanteśakṣe tu parjanyaḥ jayayāmyage
tasyāgneye tu māhendraṃ sūryānte dvīpade sthitāḥ
- 8.218 tadindre tu nyaset satyaṃ satyetigaṃ bhṛśaṃ nyaset
tasya yāmyantarikṣas tu hutabhuk svadīśisthitāḥ
- 8.219 pūṣāpye pāvakākhyasya vitathas tasya nairṛte
vitathādau ca bhṛṅgāntā dvīpadāḥ paṅktisaṃsthitāḥ

C f36v

A f72v

B f64r

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

215a skanda] em.; śkanda A; kanda BC

215b aryama] em.; ayāma ABC

216a jambhaḥ] em.; jambha ABC

216b pāparākṣasi] AB; pāparākṣī C

217c ye tu] BC; [[tu]]yetu A

218c antarikṣas] AB; antarīkṣas C

219c bhṛṅgāntā] AC; bhṛṅgāntāḥ B

219d paṅkti] C; pakti AB

- 8.220 hariṇā padam ekaṃ tu tatsaumye pitaras tathā
dauvārikas tu tadvāyoḥ śoṣāntā dvipade sthitāḥ
- 8.221 rogaindraikapade bhadre tatpūrve vāyus tadvidhaḥ
tadiśe nāgamādyas tu somāntā dvipadāḥ sthitāḥ
- 8.222 rigiś caikapadāvasthas tadvad aditi yāmyage
ditiś caindre padāvasthā brahmānte tu catuṣpade
- 8.223 turyāvastho marīcyādi vatsādyā dvipade bahiḥ
devatā bhogabhittis tu vatsādyante carīcaraḥ
- 8.224 īśāgnau kumbhakoṇe tu madhye ca śaraveśanam
bhavaty aṭṭālako vāstuprākārārdhavinirgamāt
- 8.225 vaṃśadvayaṃ yathāpūrvaṃ rajjavaḥ kathayāmi te
vāyvitige guṇāvasthe īśāgnau padage priye
- 8.226 svarage dve ca boddhavye rasage dve tu eva ca
marmādyāś ca yathāpūrvaṃ jñātvāṭṭālakam ārabhet

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

220c dauvārikas] em.; dvauvārikas ABC

221d somāntā] C; somāntāḥ AB

222a rigiś] AB; giriś C

• caika] AC; ceka B

222b aditi] A; ati BC

222c ditiś] AB; diti C

• caindre] A; caiṃndre B; caindra C

• padāvasthā] A; padāvastha BC

223b bahiḥ] A; bahi{ḥ} C; bahi B

224b śara] A; sara BC

225b rajjavaḥ] AB; rajjakaḥ C

226a boddhavye] AC; bodhavye B

226b rasage] BC; raśage A

226c marmādyāś ca] em.; marmādyāca A; mamādyāstu C; marmādyā B

- 8.227 prākārabhittivistāro dīrghatvena samīkṛtaḥ
bhājya pañktisamo 'trāpi samantāt tu vipaścite
- 8.228 tathā nyāsas tu devānāṃ yathā nagaravāstuvat
vaṃśarajjus tathābhūtā marmādyās tu tathaiva ca
- 8.229 vidhinānena netavyo yāvad āṭṭālakō bhavet
bhūyo 'ṭṭālaṃ punar bhittir bhittyāṭṭālakam eva ca
- 8.230 evaṃ bhrāmya caturdikṣu sakoṇaṃ vṛttam eva vā
tribhāgair bhittibandhas tu saptabhis tu carīcaraḥ
- 8.231 socchrayaṃ dvīnaraṃ bhadre bhittir yā naramānataḥ
sopānaṃ rohaṇārthaṃ tu kartavyaṃ satato bahūn
- 8.232 bhitteś cordhve tu kau kuryāt saṃvṛttaś cordhvato bhavet
vṛttādhaḥ suṣīraṃ kāryaṃ gopuro vātha jālakam

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

227c pañkti] AC; pakti B

227d samantāt] BC; samatām A

228c rajjus] A; rajjūṃs B; rajjuṃs C

229c punar] AC; puna B

• bhittir] AC; bhitti B

230c bhāgair] AC; bhāgai B

231d satatobahūn] A; satobahūn B; [-]satobahūn C

232b saṃvṛttaś] AB; savṛttaś C

- 8.233 śaranirgamaṅārthe tu yato vighrahaheṭuśaḥ
caturdikṣu bhaved dvāraṃ dvārordhve valabhī bhavet
- 8.234 adho 'bhyantarabāhye tu dvārapālāśrayaṃ kuru A f73r
saumyāpyaindrais tribhir bāhyaṃ yāmyaṃ caiva kathaṃ cana
- 8.235 sadāpi hitaṃ tad dvāraṃ yamadaṃṣṭraṃ yato matam B f64v
kimarthaṃ caiva yuddhārthaṃ nānyathā vighrahe jayaḥ
- 8.236 pratiyantraparikṣepair vāstu rudrātmako bhavet
bhūtasamkhyāpadair bāhye carakyādyā grahaiḥ saha
- 8.237 madhye nava navānāṃ tu grahāṃs tatraiva vinyaset
ādityādiś ca ketvantā madhye navapadaih sthitāḥ
- 8.238 raviṃ madhye tu vinyasya somādyaindrāditaḥ kramāt
pūrvacakrādhipaḥ somaḥ somasya padago raviḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

233cd bhaved dvāraṃ dvārordhve] C; bhavedvāraṃdvārorddhe B;
bhavedvārorddhe A

234b dvāra] AC; dvārā B

235a hitaṃ tad dvāraṃ] em.; hitatadvāraṃ ABC

235b daṃṣṭraṃ] AC; draṣṭuṃ B

236a yantra] AB; yaṃtraṃ C

236d carakyādyā] AC; carajyādyā B

• saha] C; sahaḥ AB

237c ādityādiś] A; ādityāś BC

238c somaḥ] em.; soma ABC

- 8.239 bhūsutādyān nyased bhūya agnyādyam īśagocare
aṅgāro 'dhipatis tadvad agnicakre tu suvrate
- 8.240 somādityabudhādyāms tu punar ekakramān nyaset
budho 'dhipas tathā yāmye vinyasec cakramadhyataḥ
- 8.241 somāṅgāarakasūryās tu gīrvāṇasacivāditaḥ
nyastavyā devadeveśi yathāvad anupūrvaśaḥ
- 8.242 īticakrādhipo bhūyo devamantṛi vidur budhāḥ
somāṅgāro budhādityaḥ śukrādyānukrameṇa tu
- 8.243 āpye śukro 'dhipaḥ proktaḥ somādyā ravitatpade
śanirādyān punar nyasya vāyucakrādhipaḥ śaniḥ
- 8.244 somādyāms tu punar nyasya śanisthāne tu bhāskaraḥ
rāhuketvantagaṃ nyastvā rāhuḥ saumyādhipaḥ priye

C f37r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

A omits 239c-241a somam, skipping from one aṅgār- to the next.

239a bhūsutādyān] AB; bhūsutādyā C

240a budhādyāms] B; budhādyās C

241a somāṅgāarakasūryās] conj.; somamaṅgārasūryās B; somamaṅgārasūryās C;

aṅgāarakasya sūryas A

241b gīrvāṇa] BC; gī[[ṇa]]rvāṇa A

242a bhūyo] em.; bhūya BC; bhūye A

242b mantrī] BC; maṃtrā A

243c ādyān] AB; ādyāḥ C

244a somādyāms B; somādyās AC

244c saumyādhipaḥ] em.; somyādhipaḥ ABC

- 8.245 somādyendrādīto nyasya saumyeśe raviketukau
īśacakrādhipaḥ ketuḥ somādyā bhāskarāvadhi
- 8.246 nyastvaivaṃ tu vidhānena grahavāstur ato mataḥ
vaṃśādyāṃ pūrvavat pātya marmādyāṃs tu vilakṣayet
- 8.247 prākārānte tu sāmīpye yatrāvasthānaṃ bhavet
caturdikṣv aṣṭakam cāpi ṣoḍaśaṃ vā prakalpayet
- 8.248 citivāstuṃ pravakṣyāmi śṛṇuṣv ekamaṇā priye
grahāṇāṃ rākṣasānāṃ ca smaśāne pitṛdevatām
- 8.249 same bhūtavibhakte tu śatārdhārdhapaḍaṃ bhavet
vyoma madhyendrato vāyur hutabhug yāmya āpyakam
- 8.250 saumye dharāṃ tu vinyasya madhyacakre vidur budhāḥ
pūrve vāyuyṃ punar nyasya tadyāmye khavahniṃ nyaset

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

245a somādyendrādīto AB; somyādyendrādīto C

245c īśa] em.; īśaś ABC

245b saumyeśe BC; somyeśe A

245d bhāskarāvadhi C; bhāskarāvadhiḥ AB

246a nyastvaivaṃ] em.; nyastvevaṃ ABC

• vidhānena] AC; vidhāne B

246c vaṃśādyāṃ AB; vaṃśādyāḥ C

246d marmādyāṃs AB; marmādyās C

247a prākārānte tu sāmīpye] A; prākārāntesāmīpye[-] C; prākārāntesāmīpye B

247b yatrāvasthānaṃ] AC; yatravasthānaṃ B

247c catur] AC; catu B

248a vāstuṃ] AC; vāstu B

248d devatāṃ AB; devatāḥ C

249b śatārdhārdhapaḍaṃ] A; śatārdhārdhapaḍaṃ BC

249c vāyur] C; vāyuh AB

249d bhug] C; bhuk AB

250a saumye] AB; saume C

250d khavahniṃ] AB; kha[-]vahniṃ C

- 8.251 jvalāpye kaṃ punar nyasya tatsaumye pṛthivīm nyaset
yāmye 'gñiṃ ca tathā nyasya agnyāpye vāyukhaṃ bhavet
- 8.252 khasaumye tu jalaṃ nyasya jalendre tu dharā bhavet
āpye kaṃ tu punar nyasya tatsaumye gatipāvakaḥ
- 8.253 pāvendre tu nyased vyoma vyomāntake dharā bhavet
saumye dharāṃ punar nyasya dharendre gatipāvakaḥ
- 8.254 tadyāmye kaṃ punar nyasya āpyāpye vyomakaṃ nyaset
evaṃ kramāt suvinyasya carakyādyāgrahaḥ saha
- 8.255 yathāpūrvaṃ nyased bāhye dikkoṇasthitavigrahāḥ
vaṃśadvayaṃ tathā pātya rajjuś cāṣṭau śṛṇu priye
- 8.256 catasro dvipadā jñeyās catasro 'nya guṇātmakāḥ
marmādyātra yathāpūrvaṃ jñātvā samyak samācaret
- 8.257 bhūtātmako yato bhadre bhūtavāstus tathocyate
ity ete vāstavaḥ khyātā ḡhavāstusamanvitāḥ

ityādye jayadrathādhikāre dvādaśasāhasre
piṅgalāmate vāstvadhikāro nāma aṣṭamaḥ prakaraṇaḥ

B f65r
A f73v

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 251b pṛthivīm] AC; pṛthivī B
 251c yāmye 'gñiṃ] BC; yāmyagniṃ A
 252a jalaṃ] AC; jala B
 252c punar] AC; puna B
 253c dharāṃ] em.; dharā ABC
 254a yāmyekaṃ] AB; yāmekaṃ C
 254c suvinyasya] AB; savinyasya C
 254d carakyādyā] AC: carajyādyā B • saha] BC; sahaḥ A
 255c dvayaṃ] A; dvaya BC
 256b catasro 'nya] AC; cataśronya B
 256d samācaret] AC; mācaret B
 257b vāstus tathocyate] BC; vāstutatocyate A
 257c vāstavaḥ] AC; vāstava{ḥ} B
 after 257 nāma; C; nāmaḥ AB; aṣṭamaḥ A; [- - -] BC